

TYOLOGY OPTIONS OF GLOBALISMS IN THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

“The functioning of globalisms in modern Russian” is devoted to identifying the derivational potential of globalisms, the features of their functioning in modern Russian, and also presents options for the typology of globalisms. An analysis of the functioning of globalisms in the Russian language makes it possible to identify a certain pattern: each newly emerging slang unit not only provides informal communication for the speakers of this jargon, but also serves their professional (social) needs, and, as it is used, claims to become an element of the lexical system of a general literary language . At the same time, the computer, economic, sports and consumer (including pragmatonyms) global vocabulary of the modern Russian language is most intensively replenished and functioning.

Keywords: globalisms, internationalization, linguoculture, jargon, professionalisms, types of globalisms.

INTRODUCTION

Systematization of the global layer of the international vocabulary of the Russian language is possible on the basis of several approaches. In the first approximation, the thematic differentiation attracts attention. It generally coincides with the traditional idea of the main thematic layers of international vocabulary. At the same time, my observation, presented in many works, shows that the most intensively replenished computer (*аккаунт ассемблер, бан, бенчмарк, блог, лаг* etc.), economic (*антидемпинг, аутсорсинг, брендинг, гудвилл* etc.) , sports (*армрестлинг, бёрди, бодибилдинг, борд, воркаут* etc.) and especially consumer (*бárбершóп, бьюти, бренд, бургер, вóппер, гламур* etc.) global vocabulary.

METHODS

At the same time, the computer, economic, sports and consumer (including pragmatonyms [see: Fomenko, 2009]) global vocabulary of the modern Russian language is most intensively replenished and functioning. The last thematic group has never before been singled out as part of the international vocabulary, since it did not represent a quantitatively significant phenomenon. However, by the end of the last

century, the consumer society and the values and behavioral standards it propagated acquired a global character and became the most important (perhaps the main and most massive) subject of international communication [see: Inglehart, 1997]. The culture of consumption forms tastes, desires, values, norms of behavior, interests. Consumer vocabulary became their verbalization. Entire lexico-semantic groups associated with various aspects of consumer culture came to sub-global Russian from global English: household appliances, clothes, shoes, food.

For a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon of interest to us, we offer several options for classifying globalisms: by the method of design, by the presence / absence of a concept in Russian linguistic culture, by the sphere of use, using analytical schemes that we have already used in the analysis of internationalisms [see: Bogoslovskaya, Murashko, Kosyreva 2016].

RESULTS

Types of globalisms according to the method of registration in Russian. According to the method of registration in Russian as a recipient language, the following groups of globalisms can be distinguished:

1. Globalisms changed graphically and conveyed by the appropriate means of the Russian language without any structural changes, for example: тренд (trend), троллинг (trolling) etc.

Some of these words are formed in Russian in accordance with the pronunciation and phonetic appearance that is in English (*селфи* – selfie, *сайт* – site, *флуд* – flood etc.), the forms of others indicate that the original was taken written and graphic form of the English word (*бан* – ban, *спам* – spam etc.).

2. Globalisms with partial morphological substitution.

Usually, the affixal part or the element of a compound word is substituted, cf.: веб-форум (web forum), микро-флуд (micro flood).

3. Globalisms morphologically formed by means of the Russian language, for example, *гузлить* – (to) google, etc. Basically, such globalisms are derivatives of the first type of globalisms.

4. Globalisms that changed their phonetic appearance during the transition from English to Russian.

One of the reasons for the change in the phonetic appearance of the word is the lack of a corresponding sound in the Russian language. In particular, in all globalisms, the sound [r], which is absent in the English word, is clearly pronounced, i.e. the speaker is guided by the graphic appearance of the word: геймер – gamer, оверквотинг – overquoting etc.

5. Globalisms borrowed from Greek and Latin elements: бета-ридер – beta-reader etc.

The expediency of singling out such words into a separate group is that “the specifics of the words-terms created in this way is that they “have no homeland” of a living source of borrowing, like most foreign words. These terms, which currently constitute a significant lexical layer in every language, testify to the internationalization of certain categories of vocabulary - a trend that is noted in the linguistic literature as a specific feature inherent in modern relations between languages and peoples" [Akulenko 1972: 78-79].

DISCUSSION

It should be noted that in the proposed typology of globalisms according to the method of registration in Russian, we did not identify examples of two possible types known from the classification of English borrowings on this basis, proposed by V.R. Bogoslovskaya [see: Bogoslovskaya 2003]. These are borrowings with elements of tracing and two-component borrowings of complex English words with hyphenated writing. In our opinion, this is quite natural, since the unique elements of the recipient language, being included in the design of globalisms, bringing the latter closer to native speakers, would at the same time move globalism away from its universal image recognizable in global communication.

Types of globalisms by the presence or absence of a concept in Russian linguistic culture. Depending on the presence or absence of the concept designated by globalism in Russian linguistic culture, the global vocabulary of the Russian language can be divided into three groups:

1. Globalisms that have penetrated into Russian along with new concepts (eg, *скроллинг, оверквотинг, бан, флейм, мультипост* etc.).
2. Globalisms, naming concepts that were previously known to native speakers, but had a different plan of expression (for example, trend - trend, message - message, message, etc.). In this case, globalism, as a rule, either refines the meaning or simplifies the nomination, embodying the fundamental trend towards the economy of language means.

It should be noted that among the globalisms there are no words denoting concepts (phenomena) inherent in a foreign culture. Such foreign borrowings are traditionally classified as exoticisms [Krysin, 1991, 1994; Dyakov, 2001] and perform only a nominative function, playing an exclusively decorative role. This seems to be quite natural. In the situation of English-language technological and cultural intervention in the conditions of almost instantaneous messaging in global communication, the concepts that were attributes of a foreign language culture quickly and firmly take root in Russian linguistic culture and lose their decorative touch. Therefore, we tend to believe that “globalisms-exoticisms” are impossible by definition.

Types of globalisms by sphere of use. The sphere of use of globalisms is not limited solely to the realities of Internet communication, as it may seem at first glance, but has the potential to spread in the socio-economic, socio-political spheres. The correspondence of specific words-globalisms to one or another type of lexical units depends on the depth of penetration of the concept designated by it into the Russian linguoculture as a whole.

1. Globalisms are commonly used. This group includes words that are fully mastered by the Russian language: these are commonly used terms (for example, *спам, селфи, сайт, тренд* etc.), as well as official, stylistically neutral terms generally accepted among specialists (for example, *аккаунт, логин, твит* etc.). others).

2. Uncommon globalisms are not fully mastered by the Russian language. Their further distribution by class depends on the degree of mastering the concepts denoted by such globalisms.

Uncommon globalisms are represented by the following groups:

1) professionalisms, which, in turn, include highly specialized terms (for example, flood and its varieties: nickname flood, smile flood, micro flood, presence flood, etc.);

2) jargon that has an even narrower scope of use (for example, slang for gamers, hackers, pranksters, etc.).

It should be noted that there are two ideas about the essence of professionalisms in lexicology:

- professionalism - colloquial term;
- professionalism is close to the term, but it is not.

The difference between the term and professionalism, according to A.V. Kalinin lies in the fact that the term is completely official, accepted and legalized in a given science, industry, etc. designation, the name of a concept, and professionalism is a semi-official word that is not a strict, scientific designation of a concept [Kalinin 1978: 140].

With regard to the global vocabulary, such a division is not relevant: the selection of colloquial terms from its array does not affect the system as a whole, and not only because the stylistic marking of these words does not prevent them from denoting the same concepts that are realized in the meaning of a commonly used term, but also because, on the one hand, the concept of the norm in Russian linguistic culture is mobile, and on the other hand, the written fixation and approbation of colloquial terms in Internet communication occurs so quickly that the term remains “colloquial” for a very short time.

It should be especially noted that the high speed and ease of interlingual interaction in global communication lead to the fact that primordial jargons begin to experience competition from global ones. For example, the familiar *братан* in youth

jargon is increasingly adjacent to bro (bro is an abbreviation for brother - brother) - jargon with the meaning " **бро** ", " братан ", " кореш ", which appeared in American English relatively recently, but has already gained global distribution.

For example:

"*Бро, сорян, я не хотел!*" In addition, even such a famous character as Sashka the Bearded used to ask for a plea in front of the police. Thus, he, as it were, asked to understand him and, if possible, forgive him.

In the above fragment, it is interesting to use the jargon of the *сорян*, which goes back to the borrowed interjection sorry! (sorry), which in the 1990s. was perceived as exoticism, in the 2000s - as barbarism, and in the 2010s. - as one of the options for designing a social ritual of apology in global communication. And the derivational activity of the *сорян* jargon (*соряныч, соррямба, соряшечка* etc.) once again demonstrates the depth of penetration of the elements of global English into the system of the subglobal Russian language.

CONCLUSION

At one time, E.V. Marinova noted that "the rapid Russification of the word (inclusion in the system of the Russian language, processing at all language levels) does not yet make it a full-fledged unit of the language in the sense that was put into this concept by the traditional theory of borrowing, i.e. commonly used, stylistically neutral word" (Marinova, 2008, p. 38), that "many words have undergone phonetic adaptation, are written in Cyrillic, have their own strictly individual meaning, have derivatives, but at the same time remain on the periphery of the language within any linguistic microsystem (usually serving one or another professional area)" [Marinova, 2008, p. 37-38]. However, our observations show that in the era of linguistic globalization, the speed of adaptation processes is of fundamental importance. Moreover, the most active lexico-semantic shifts, the most vivid language game, take place precisely on the linguistic periphery. At the same time, we do not consider the attribution of vocabulary to any narrow professional field as something flawed, otherwise we will have to consider all industry terminology that is not included in the layer of commonly used vocabulary as inferior.

Globalisms have become part of the lexical system of the Russian language at the beginning of the 21st century. The above options for the typology of globalisms are intended to bring us closer to understanding their place in this system. And the question of the usefulness of borrowings will be attributed to the costs of linguistic purism, which must be overcome and are overcome by the science of language.

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